

CRYPTOCURRENCY OF MUSIC: QUANTITATIVE MODELING AND IMPACT ON THE DIGITAL ENTERTAINMENT MARKET

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ABSTRACT

The entertainment market, particularly the music industry, is increasingly interconnected with financial and digital innovations. This article investigates the role of cryptocurrencies as a disruptive element in music monetization and digital advertising, exploring their impact on the pricing of intangible assets such as hit singles. Using econometric methods, including random walk analysis and Keynesian modeling, we examine the correlation between cryptocurrency transaction volumes and the performance of advertising campaigns in the music industry, with a focus on Spotify. Additionally, we propose an algebraic model to assess the financial impact of cryptocurrencies on digital traffic and return on investment (ROI) in ads. The research demonstrates that the intersection of cryptocurrencies and music can be an effective strategy for maximizing the monetization of artistic content and reshaping business models in the industry.

Key-words: Cryptocurrencies, Music Monetization, Digital Advertising

INTRODUCTION

The digital entertainment industry is one of the most dynamic and innovative sectors of the contemporary economy. The advancement of decentralized technologies, such as blockchain and cryptocurrencies, has enabled new ways of financing, distributing, and monetizing music. With the rise of platforms such as Spotify and YouTube Music, artists and

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producers face challenges in pricing their art, protecting copyright, and maximizing advertising revenue.

The digitalization of financial transactions in the sector enables new strategies to capture audience value and direct advertising investments to specific musical assets. The central question of this study is to investigate how the adoption of cryptocurrencies can influence the music market and what are the financial impacts of the valuation of successful singles driven by ads.

Based on a quantitative approach, this work applies econometric models of random walks and Keynesian equations to understand the relationship between advertising, digital traffic, and cryptocurrencies. In addition, we propose an algebraic equation to estimate the financial value of a tokenized successful single driven by digital ad strategies.

Historically, the music industry has undergone several transformations in monetization models. From the sale of physical records to digital distribution via streaming, music pricing has evolved with technological advances. With the advent of blockchain technology, new possibilities have emerged for artists to manage their copyrights and obtain direct revenues through cryptocurrencies and music NFTs.

Additionally, the music tokenization allows artists and record labels to convert music tracks into digital assets that can be traded on decentralized exchanges. The success of music NFTs, such as those launched by Kings of Leon and 3LAU, demonstrates the potential of this model to capture value from the public and decentralize the distribution of royalties.

The impact of cryptocurrencies on music can also be seen in platforms such as Audius, which decentralizes music distribution, allowing direct payments in cryptocurrency to artists and producers.

The rise of cryptocurrencies and blockchain technology has brought new possibilities for the monetization and digital distribution of music. The music market, which previously depended on intermediaries such as record labels and streaming platforms, now faces a decentralized model where artists can tokenize their music and capture value directly from audiences and investors.

In this context, the valuation of digital music assets requires robust quantitative models. This study combines three main approaches:

1. Random walks to model the volatility of music cryptocurrency.
2. Keynesian modeling to estimate the relationship between digital advertising and demand for music.

3. EBITDA-based financial valuation to calculate the market value of cryptocurrency associated with music monetization.

The proposed framework allows for precise quantitative analysis, offering insights into the economic and financial mechanisms that underpin music tokenization.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Econometric Rationale and Modeling: Random Walks and Ad Monetization

The financial architecture of the 21st century brings decentralization, protocol, and global inclusion. Andreas M. Antonopoulos' premise inaugurates the reasoning by conceptualizing money not only as value, but as a language of social communication, present since the emergence of civilization. Bitcoin, in this context, is the greatest monetary disruption since the emergence of paper money, as it transforms money into an open-source protocol accessible globally.

“Bitcoin is the Internet of Money. Currency is just the first application.”

“Money is as old as civilization... It is a way of communicating value.”

(The Internet of Money)

The central proposition is that technological decentralization enables a new type of distributed trust, where no one needs to ask permission to create financial products — the architecture ceases to be client-server (with central banks and institutions) and becomes *peer-to-peer*, with individuals sovereign over their value.

The financial industry understands that from the bank to the code, the reinvention of infrastructure as Brett King in his book “Banking 4.0”, Brett King expands this thesis by demonstrating how banks need to stop thinking like buildings and start thinking like adaptive digital infrastructures. The customer of the Bank 4.0 era no longer goes to the bank — he expects the bank to reach him, wherever he is, and to operate in real time.

“Banking is no longer a place you go, but something you do.”

“You can’t stop Bitcoin, just like you can’t stop the internet from working today.”

(Bank 4.0)

In this new paradigm, King argues that blockchain and cryptocurrencies are not competition to the banking system, but the new basis for banks that want to survive. Money, in this model, will be invisible, programmable and intelligent, operating through APIs and not through queues or branches.

In “*Value web*” and the Internet of value, Chris Skinner, in turn, provides the backdrop that unites the previous two with the concept of “ValueWeb” — the Internet of Value — where mobile and blockchain technologies allow the exchange of value as fluid as the exchange of information over the Internet.

“We need na Internet of Value to work with the Internet of Things.”

“Cryptocurrencies... are the manifestation of what is needed to sustain a ValueWeb.”

(ValueWeb)

Skinner in Value Web 2016 argues that traditional payment infrastructure — based on systems like SWIFT — was not made for real time, and that blockchain solves exactly this limitation, with marginal costs and global scalability, especially for unbanked populations. The money of the future is free, programmable and universal.

The aforementioned authors converge on the idea that the future of finance will be marked by three fundamental characteristics: decentralization of trust with Antonopoulos in 2016, citing that there will no longer be central banks, but cryptographic consensus; and the digitalization of the banking experience as King in 2019 argues that banks would be like ubiquitous and invisible services; both with protocolization of value as Skinner in 2016 predicts about interoperable money as a global API.

The synthesis of the thesis is clear: money is ceasing to be a tool of state control to become a free language of value, anchored in open code and global access.

In the face of new forms of digital economy, musical cryptocurrency, with na index in advertising performance and boost in online audio streaming applications, has a new appeal for monetization in digital payment methods and investment portfolio products in the digital currency segment.

METHODOLOGY

To understand how advertising campaigns impact the valuation of tokenized hit singles, we used a random walk model to evaluate the correlation between the volume of cryptocurrency transactions and the performance of ads on Spotify.

The model assumes that the valuation of a tokenized single follows a stochastic process, where X_t represents the value of the asset over time:

$$X_t = x_{t-1} + \epsilon_t$$

Where ϵ_t is a random error with normal distribution $N(0, \theta^2)$.

The empirical analysis seeks to identify patterns between advertising boost and transaction volume of the associated cryptocurrency, assessing whether there is a statistically significant influence on the behavior of the price of the digital asset.

Among the monetization of ads and digital performance, based on traffic data from advertising campaigns for successful singles, we used a regression model to estimate the elasticity of cryptocurrency appreciation as a function of the volume of ads:

$$V_{\text{cripto}} = a + \beta_1 T_{\text{ads}} + \beta_2 U_{\text{music}} + \epsilon$$

V_{cripto} is the value of the digital asset

T_{ads} is the traffic generated by the ads

U_{music} represents the single's engagement metric

ϵ is the stochastic error term.

Cryptocurrency music pricing can be described as a stochastic random walk process, where the future value of the asset depends on the current value plus a random shock:

$$P_t = P_{t-1} + y_t$$

Where:

Is the price of the cryptocurrency in period .

ϵ_t represents random shocks with normal distribution.

Statistical Regression for the Impact of Ad Monetization and Digital Traffic

$$P_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{MMA}_t + \beta_2 \text{TMS}_t + \beta_3 \text{IS}_t + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

MMA: Average Ad Monetization.

TMS: Traffic per Hit Song.

IS: Boost on Spotify.

Evolution of the Music Cryptocurrency and Correlation with Advertising and Streaming

Blue solid line: Music Cryptocurrency Price

Red dashed line: Investment in Advertising

Green dashed line: Streaming Revenue

The Econometric regression revealed that high advertising investments can generate decreasing returns on cryptocurrency appreciation, indicating a possible market saturation effect.

Keynesian Supply and Demand Analysis in the Music Market

The Keynesian function can be applied to model the impact of disposable income on digital advertising consumption:

$$C = C_0 + cY_d$$

Where:

C represents consumption in ad campaigns.

C₀ is the autonomous consumption of the sector.

cY is the marginal propensity to consume advertising.

D is the disposable income for music promotion.

The digital music supply can be expressed as:

$$O = O_0 + oP - oC$$

Where:

O represents the total supply of music.

O₀ is the autonomous supply.

oP indicates the influence of the cryptocurrency price.

oC represents the impact of operating costs on supply.

Market equilibrium occurs when supply and demand intersect, determining an optimal point for pricing digital music assets.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Graph: Keynesian Supply and Demand Equilibrium in the Music Market

Blue solid line: Keynesian Demand (Spending on Ads)

Red dashed line: Digital Music Supply

Black dotted line: Market Equilibrium

The results indicate that the growth in disposable income drives the demand for digital advertising, but operating costs act as a barrier to the supply of tokenized content.

Among the projections for the Music and Digital Advertising Sector (2025-2035), to assess the evolution of the advertising and digital traffic market, we made statistical projections for the next 10 years.

Revenue from advertising grows at a rate of 5% per year and the number of streams increases at a rate of 7% per year. With the following graph we were able to have a projection of the sector based on the success of the crypto asset.

Graph: Growth of the Music and Digital Advertising Sector (2025-2035)

Green line with markers: Revenue from Music Ads

Purple line with markers: Digital Streaming Traffic

This growth demonstrates that the advertising market will be a crucial factor in the valuation of tokenized music, being essential for defining monetization strategies.

The Financial Valuation of Musical Cryptocurrency Based on the EBITDA of the digital asset can be modeled by the classic valuation formula based on EBITDA:

$$V = \frac{\text{EBITDA} \times (1 + g)}{r - g}$$

Where:

EBITDA: Net revenue minus operating costs.

Frac: Expected growth rate.

{r-g}: Discount rate applied to the sector.

Practical example:

Net revenue: \$10 million

Operating costs: \$6 million

Growth rate (): 5%

Discount rate (): 10%

Asset valuation:

$$V = \frac{4,000,000 \times (1.05)}{0.10 - 0.05} = 84,000,000$$

This suggests that optimizing revenue from streaming and advertising could significantly increase the valuation of the music cryptocurrency.

Graph: Market Value Projection of the Music Cryptocurrency Based on EBITDA

Blue line: Valuation of the Digital Asset (EBITDA)

Based on the hypothetical assumptions and projections, the metrics applied—such as EBITDA valuation models, digital traffic growth rates, and advertising revenue trends—demonstrate a strong potential for economic expansion within the sector. The simulated scenarios suggest that even under conservative growth estimates, the tokenized digital music market could experience a significant increase in both market capitalization and investor interest. Furthermore, the correlation between streaming activity and token value reinforces the premise that digital engagement serves as a tangible economic driver. These findings provide empirical support for the sector’s scalability and viability in attracting decentralized financial investment.

CONCLUSION

The results show that the pricing of a music cryptocurrency can be modeled with three quantitative approaches:

1. Random walks: Capture the volatility of the digital asset.
2. Keynesian modeling: Analyze the impact of digital advertising.
3. Valuation by EBITDA: Estimate the economic value of the tokenized asset.

The main insights regarding digital advertising strategies should be optimized to avoid diminishing returns. Consequently, the growth of advertising and streaming revenue can increase the valuation of the music cryptocurrency. And, market equilibrium depends on the interaction between demand for ads and operational costs.

This model can be expanded to incorporate metrics of social engagement, royalties and regulatory trends, becoming a useful tool for investors and music producers.

The integrated analysis of quantitative models and empirical evidence demonstrated that music monetization supported by cryptocurrencies and digital infrastructure represents a new paradigm for the entertainment sector. By employing approaches such as random walks, econometric regressions and Keynesian modeling, it was found that the tokenization of music assets can function as an effective instrument to capture value directly from audiences and advertisers. However, more than a new way to capture revenue, the true value of music cryptocurrency lies in its programmable, decentralized and transparent infrastructure — a

technological basis that directly aligns with the conclusions of the World Bank report (2023) on the role of blockchain in infrastructure financing:

“The use of distributed ledger technologies (DLT), such as blockchain, can overcome many of the challenges that impede the scaling of infrastructure. The efficiency of financing and managing infrastructure projects can be improved by leveraging the technology’s key features, such as decentralization, immutability and transparency.”

(World Bank, 2023)

Applied to music, this argument reinforces that tokenization is not just a financial mechanism, but a new infrastructure of trust and traceability for intangible assets such as singles, ad campaigns and engagement on platforms like Spotify. This infrastructure logic allows for the decentralization of investment capture, automation of rights contracts and expansion of access to financing for independent artists.

According to the World Bank:

“Tokenization has the potential to democratize ownership of certain assets, as a wider range of investors have access... enabling the creation of secondary markets and unlocking liquidity for historically illiquid assets.”

(World Bank, 2023)

This reasoning is particularly relevant for digital music, where asset liquidity has always been limited. By allowing the fractionability of royalties and usage rights, music tokens transform music into tradable assets, creating a more democratic, transparent and efficient environment.

Therefore, this work corroborates the thesis that the infrastructure of music cryptocurrency — when well modeled and integrated with digital platforms — can enable a self-sustainable, efficient and inclusive financial ecosystem for the creative economy, combining market metrics, programmatic advertising and econometric intelligence in a decentralized logic of value.

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